

Convergence Rate and Iteration Complexity of Trust-Region Method for Set-Valued Maps

Suprova Ghosh

Department of Mathematical Science, Indian Institute of Technology (BHU), suprovaghosh.rs.mat19@itbhu.ac.in

Abstract. In this paper, we present convergence-rate and iteration-complexity analysis of a recently proposed trust-region method for set optimization problems (TRM-SOP), where the objective is a set-valued map generated by finitely many vector-valued functions (Ghosh et al. 2025b). We establish that the method achieves a linear convergence rate under mild assumptions, and that the number of iterations required to reach a K -critical point with accuracy ϵ is bounded by

$$O(\sqrt{m} \Sigma \epsilon^{-2}),$$

where m denotes the number of components in each vector-valued function and Σ is the optimality gap. Notably, this bound is dimension-free with respect to the decision space and closes existing theoretical gaps in the performance guarantees of trust-region algorithms for set optimization. These results provide the first iteration-complexity theory and convergence-rate analysis for trust-region methods in the set-valued context.

Key words: Trust-region method, Set Optimization, Convergence rate, Iteration complexity

1. Introduction

Set optimization is a branch of optimization that is concerned with minimizing or maximizing set-valued objectives where decision variables may represent vectors, intervals, or more complex structures. Formally, the set optimization problem (SOP) is written as

$$\text{minimize } F(x) \quad \text{subject to } x \in U,$$

where $F : U \rightrightarrows V$ assigns to each $x \in U$ a subset of a vector space V . The solution concept of SOP rely on cone-based orderings or set inclusions. This type of optimization is crucial in finance (Mastrogioacomo and Rocca 2021), optimal control (Hamel and Visetti 2020), game theory (Hamel and Löhne 2018), and economics (Hamel and Heyde 2010), where set-valued objectives naturally arise. Over the past decade, several methods have been developed for solving SOPs, including derivative-free (Jahn 2015), steepest descent (Bouza et al. 2021), sorting-based (Günther et al. 2019), branch-and-bound (Eichfelder et al. 2020), complete-lattice (Löhne 2025), conjugate gradient (kumar et al. 2025), Newton and quasi-Newton (Ghosh et al. 2024, 2025a), and recently the TRM-SOP (Ghosh et al. 2025b).

Among these, TRM-SOP is one of the promising and efficient algorithms with high convergence guarantees, particularly for solving high-dimensional SOPs. TRM-SOP solves

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} F(x), \quad F(x) = \{f^1(x), \dots, f^p(x)\},$$

where each $f^i : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is twice continuously differentiable. Overall, the method sequentially employs the technique of vectorization, oriented-distance scalarization, and trust-region method to solve the SOP. First, vectorization transforms the SOP into a class of vector optimization problems (VOPs). Next, scalarization is applied to select one specific VOP from this class. The trust-region technique is then employed to solve the chosen VOP. This involves defining a subproblem and computing a trust-region step and radius. This iterative process ensures convergence to K -critical

point (Definition 3 below). This K -critical point serves as a central concept in analyzing the rate of convergence and the iteration complexity of the method.

Iteration complexity and rate of convergence quantify how efficiently an algorithm reaches a solution with a sufficiently small stationarity or criticality measure, providing performance guarantees. Specifically, iteration complexity measures the number of iterations needed to reach K -criticality with a specified accuracy, while the rate of convergence characterizes how quickly the error decreases over iterations. We next review the literature on convergence rates and iteration complexity relevant particularly to trust-region methods.

In single-objective optimization, iteration complexity (worst-case) and convergence rate (local) of trust-region methods have been extensively studied. Classical gradient-based schemes require at most $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{-2})$ iterations to achieve $\|\nabla f(x)\| \leq \varepsilon$ (Curtis et al. 2017). By using the cubic-regularization strategy introduced by Nesterov and Polyak and later incorporated into trust-region analyses, the bound $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{-2})$ improves to $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{-3/2})$ (Nesterov and Polyak 2006, Curtis et al. 2017), and the bound $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{-3/2})$ are known to be tight (Cartis et al. 2012). Several extensions refine and generalize these results. Recursive trust-region schemes handle multiscale problems with $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{-2})$ complexity (Gratton et al. 2008), while adaptive cubic regularization achieves sharp worst-case bounds of $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{-3/2})$ (Cartis et al. 2011). Nonlinear stepsize control methods for convex optimization provide complementary worst-case iteration complexity guarantees of $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{-2})$ (Grapiglia et al. 2016, Garmanjani 2022), and unified analyses of trust-region and regularization methods similarly establish an $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{-2})$ bound for reaching a first-order critical point (Grapiglia et al. 2015). Locally, trust-region methods obtain linear convergence in stochastic nonconvex settings (Shen et al. 2020), superlinear rates with quasi-Newton SR1 (Xia and Wu 2024), and quadratic convergence under partial smoothness or error bounds (Chen et al. 2020, Fan 2020). Reinforcement-learning-based variants ensure global convergence with faster rates (Shani et al. 2020), and bi-objective stochastic problems also enjoy linear convergence guarantees (Liu and Vicente 2020).

In multiobjective optimization, trust-region methods preserve strong convergence. Superlinear local convergence is achieved for constrained problems (Bisui and Panda 2025), and q -quadratic convergence for nonconvex unconstrained problems (Carrizo et al. 2016). Regarding worst-case iteration complexity, convex smooth vector problems require at most $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{-1})$ iterations (Garmanjani 2023), while derivative-free methods attain $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{-2})$ -type bounds (scaled by the number of objectives) (Custódio et al. 2021). These results demonstrate that multiobjective trust-region methods provide provable global guarantees while efficiently handling vector-valued, nonsmooth, and constrained objectives.

Trust-region methods in scalar and multiobjective optimization already have well-established iteration-complexity and convergence rate guarantees. However, for set optimization, such theoretical results are still missing. The recently proposed TRM-SOP (Ghosh et al. 2025b) although offers global convergence and strong empirical performance, it does not quantify how fast solutions are achieved. In this paper, we address this gap with the following novel contributions:

- Under a mild assumption, we establish that the convergence rate of TRM-SOP is linear.
- Assuming bounded gradients and Hessians of the vector-valued components of set objectives, we derive an iteration-complexity bound of $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{m} \Sigma \varepsilon^{-2})$ for reaching a K -critical point. For the scalar setting, $p = 1$ and $m = 1$, our bound recovers the iteration complexity in (Grapiglia et al. 2015) for the nonconvex single-objective case.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work to present both a convergence-rate analysis and an iteration-complexity bound for a trust-region method for set optimization.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly reviews the TRM-SOP algorithm and provides some preliminaries for the method. Section 3 presents the convergence rate of TRM-SOP.

Section 4 presents the iteration complexity of TRM-SOP. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and outlines future work.

2. Preliminaries and Methodology

Following (Ghosh et al. 2025b), \mathbb{R}^n and \mathbb{R}^m are Euclidean spaces, any vector v in \mathbb{R}^n and \mathbb{R}^m are columns, and v^\top is the transpose of v . $\|\cdot\|$ denotes a norm. For any finite set \mathcal{A} , $|\mathcal{A}|$ is its cardinality, and $[k] := 1, \dots, k$. A nonempty set $K \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$ is a cone if $ty \in K$ for all $y \in K$ and $t \geq 0$. It is pointed if $K \cap (-K) = \{0\}$, convex if $K + K = K$, and solid if $\text{int}(K) \neq \emptyset$. Such a cone defines the partial order $y \preceq_K z$ when $z - y \in K$, and the strict order $y \prec_K z$ when $z - y \in \text{int}(K)$. Throughout, K is a convex, pointed, closed, and solid cone in \mathbb{R}^m . The main objective of TRM-SOP is to identify a K -critical point, whose definition is given below. Other definitions, such as the *partition set*, *oriented distance scalarization*, and its properties, are also provided, as these concepts are essential for understanding the underlying framework of TRM-SOP.

DEFINITION 1. (Bouza et al. 2021)

(i) For a given vector $v \in \mathbb{R}^m$, the map $I_v : \mathbb{R}^n \rightrightarrows [p]$ is defined by

$$I_v(x) := \{i \in [p] : f^i(x) = v\},$$

where the map $I : \mathbb{R}^n \rightrightarrows [p]$ is given by $I(x) := \{i \in [p] : f^i(x) \in \text{Min}(F(x), K)\}$.

(ii) The cardinality function $\omega : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined by $\omega(x) := |\text{Min}(F(x), K)|$.

DEFINITION 2. (Bouza et al. 2021) For a given $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, consider an enumeration $\{v_1^{\bar{x}}, v_2^{\bar{x}}, \dots, v_{\omega(\bar{x})}^{\bar{x}}\}$ of the set $\text{WMin}(F(\bar{x}), K)$. The *partition set* at \bar{x} is defined by

$$P_{\bar{x}} := I_{v_1^{\bar{x}}}(\bar{x}) \times I_{v_2^{\bar{x}}}(\bar{x}) \times \dots \times I_{v_{\omega(\bar{x})}^{\bar{x}}}(\bar{x}).$$

Throughout the paper, for a given $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, we denote $\bar{\omega} := \omega(\bar{x})$, and a generic element of the partition set $P_{\bar{x}}$ is denoted by $\bar{a} := (\bar{a}_1, \bar{a}_2, \dots, \bar{a}_{\bar{\omega}})$.

DEFINITION 3 (CRITICAL POINT FOR (SOP_K^l) (GHOSH ET AL. 2025B)). A point $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is said to be a K -critical point of (SOP_K^l) if there does not exist any $\bar{a} \in P_{\bar{x}}$ and $\bar{s} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that

$$\nabla f^{\bar{a}_j}(\bar{x})^\top \bar{s} \prec_K 0 \text{ for all } j \in [\omega(\bar{x})],$$

where for any $j \in [\omega(\bar{x})]$, the notation $\nabla f^{\bar{a}_j}(\bar{x})^\top s \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is given by

$$\nabla f^{\bar{a}_j}(\bar{x})^\top s := \left(\nabla f^{\bar{a}_{j,1}}(\bar{x})^\top s, \nabla f^{\bar{a}_{j,2}}(\bar{x})^\top s, \dots, \nabla f^{\bar{a}_{j,m}}(\bar{x})^\top s \right)^\top, s \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Note that if we consider $p = 1$, then $F(x) = \{f^1(x)\}$ and then K -critical point of (SOP_K^l) reduces to the K -critical point of the vector optimization problem $f^1(x)$.

DEFINITION 4. (Ansari et al. 2018) Let $\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^m)$. A function $\Delta_{\mathcal{A}} : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{\pm\infty\} =: \bar{\mathbb{R}}$ defined by

$$\Delta_{\mathcal{A}}(y) := d_{\mathcal{A}}(y) - d_{\mathcal{A}^c}(y), y \in \mathbb{R}^m,$$

is called the oriented distance function, where $d_{\mathcal{A}}(y) := \inf_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \|y - a\|$. By convention, for any $y \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $d_{\emptyset}(y) = +\infty$, and hence, $\Delta_{\emptyset}(y) = +\infty$, whereas $\Delta_{\mathbb{R}^m}(y) = -\infty$.

LEMMA 1. (Ansari et al. 2018, Zaffaroni 2003)

- (i) Δ_{-K} is Lipschitz continuous with Lipschitz constant 1;
- (ii) $\Delta_{-K}(y) < 0$ if and only if $y \in \text{int}(-K)$.
- (iii) $\Delta_{-K}(y) = 0$ if and only if $y \in \text{bd}(-K)$.
- (iv) $\Delta_{-K}(y) > 0$ if and only if $y \in \text{int}[(-K)^c]$.
- (v) $\Delta_{-K}(y + z) = \Delta_{-K-z}(y)$ for all $y, z \in \mathbb{R}^m$.
- (vi) $\Delta_{-K}(\lambda y) = \lambda \Delta_{\lambda^{-1}(-K)}(y)$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and $\lambda > 0$.
- (vii) $\Delta_{-K}(y + z) \leq \Delta_{-K}(y) + \Delta_{-K}(z)$ and $\Delta_{-K}(y) - \Delta_{-K}(z) \leq \Delta_{-K}(y - z)$ for all $y, z \in \mathbb{R}^m$.
- (viii) Given $y, z \in \mathbb{R}^m$, if $y \prec z$ (resp., $y \preceq z$), then $\Delta_{-K}(y) < \Delta_{-K}(z)$ (resp., $\Delta_{-K}(y) \leq \Delta_{-K}(z)$).

Next, we briefly recall the TRM-SOP algorithm for finding a K -critical point of the set optimization problem

$$(\preceq_K^l)\text{-}\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} F(x), \quad (\text{SOP}_K^l)$$

where $F = \{f^i\}_{i \in [p]}$ and each $f^i : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ has components $f^{i,j}$, that is,

$$f^i(x) = (f^{i,1}(x), \dots, f^{i,m}(x))^{\top}.$$

The method starts from an arbitrary initial point x_0 (which is finite) and aims to generate a sequence of iterates $\{x_k\}$ that converges to a K -critical point. To generate x_{k+1} from x_k , a direction s_k must be chosen. For this purpose, the following sequence is employed: vectorization, scalarization, and a trust-region step.

Vectorization and Scalarization. Using Definitions 2–3, Lemma 2 (Ghosh et al. 2025b), (SOP_K^l) is converted to the following class of VOPs:

$$(\preceq_{\bar{K}})\text{-}\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} \tilde{f}^a(x), \quad (\text{VOP}_a)$$

for all $a = (a_1, \dots, a_{\bar{\omega}}) \in P_{\bar{x}}$ at $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^m$, where $\bar{\omega} := \omega(\bar{x})$. The vectorized function $\tilde{f}^a : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \prod_{j=1}^{\bar{\omega}} \mathbb{R}^m$ is defined by

$$\tilde{f}^a(x) := \begin{pmatrix} f^{a_1}(x) \\ \vdots \\ f^{a_{\bar{\omega}}}(x) \end{pmatrix}.$$

From this class of (VOP_a) s, one particular (VOP_a) is chosen. For this, at every x_k , an a^k is chosen from the partition set (Definition 2) P_k using the oriented distance scalarization Δ_{-K} (Definition 4). This is achieved by solving

$$(a^k, s_k) \in \underset{(a,s) \in P_k \times \mathcal{B}_k}{\text{argmin}} \Theta_{x_k}(a, s) \quad (\text{see Step 3 of Algorithm 1 in Appendix A}), \quad (1)$$

where $\Theta_{x_k} : P_k \times \mathcal{B}_k \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, for any $x_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$, is defined as

$$\Theta_{x_k}(a, s) := \max_{j \in [\omega_k]} \left\{ \Delta_{-K} \left(\nabla f^{a_j}(x_k)^{\top} s + \frac{1}{2} s^{\top} \nabla^2 f^{a_j}(x_k) s \right), \Delta_{-K}(\nabla f^{a_j}(x_k)^{\top} s) \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where P_k is the partition set, $\mathcal{B}_k := \{s \in \mathbb{R}^n : \|s\| \leq \Omega_k\}$, $\Omega_k > 0$ is the trust-region radius, and $\omega_k := \omega(x_k)$. Using (2), the function $\theta : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as

$$\theta(x_k) := \min_{(a,s) \in P_k \times \mathcal{B}_k} \Theta_{x_k}(a, s). \quad (3)$$

Theorem 4 in (Ghosh et al. 2025b) explains how this θ characterizes K -criticality. Theorem 4 also presents the termination criterion of the algorithm (Step 6 of Algorithm 1 in Appendix A).

Trust-Region Step. To select the trust-region step s_k , a minimization problem is solved whose objective is an oriented-distance scalarization of the quadratic model \tilde{m}^{a^k} associated with $(\mathcal{VOP}_{a^k}(x_k))$. To recall, \tilde{m}^{a^k} is defined componentwise as

$$\tilde{m}^{a^k}(s) := \nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s + \frac{1}{2} s^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) s, \quad j = 1, \dots, \omega_k,$$

with, for any $s \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s &:= \left(\nabla f^{a_j^k,1}(x_k)^\top s, \nabla f^{a_j^k,2}(x_k)^\top s, \dots, \nabla f^{a_j^k,m}(x_k)^\top s \right)^\top \text{ and} \\ s^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) s &:= \left(s^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k,1}(x_k) s, s^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k,2}(x_k) s, \dots, s^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k,m}(x_k) s \right)^\top, \end{aligned}$$

Using this model, the trust-region subproblem is written as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \min \quad & t \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \Delta_{-K}(\tilde{m}^{a_j^k}(s)) - t \leq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, \omega_k, \\ & \Delta_{-K}(\nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s) - t \leq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, \omega_k, \\ & \|s\| \leq \Omega_k. \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (4)$$

To decide whether the step s_k is accepted or not, and also to update the trust-region radius, (Ghosh et al. 2025b) defines a reduction ratio $\rho_k^{a_j^k}$, for each $j \in [\omega_k]$, as

$$\rho_k^{a_j^k} := - \frac{\Delta_{-K}(f^{a_j^k}(x_k + s_k) - f^{a_j^k}(x_k))}{\Delta_{-K}(m^{a_j^k}(0) - m^{a_j^k}(s_k))} \quad (\text{see Step 7 of Algorithm 1 in Appendix A}). \quad (5)$$

The step is accepted or rejected by comparing $\rho_k^{a_j^k}$ with two threshold parameters $\eta_1, \eta_2 \in (0, 1)$.

Similarly, the radius update rule compares $\rho_k^{a_j^k}$ with these thresholds and applies the factors $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in (0, 1)$, whenever the radius needs to be reduced.

Next, we derive the rate of convergence of the TRM-SOP algorithm. To do this, we denote the set of very successful iterations by \mathcal{VS} , the set of successful iterations by \mathcal{S} , and the set of unsuccessful iterations by \mathcal{N} . Starting from iteration k_0 , the numbers of very successful, successful, and unsuccessful iterations up to iteration k_ϵ are denoted by $\mathcal{VS}(k_0, k_\epsilon)$, $\mathcal{S}(k_0, k_\epsilon)$, and $\mathcal{N}(k_0, k_\epsilon)$, respectively. Also, we denote that, at any point $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the jacobian and Hessian of each f^i is given by

ATTENTION: The following displayed equation, in its current form, exceeds the column width that will be used in the published edition of your article. Please break or rewrite this equation to fit, including the equation number, within a column width of 470 pt / 165.81 mm / 6.53 in (the width of this red box).

$$\nabla f^i(x) := \left(\nabla f^{i,1}(x), \nabla f^{i,2}(x), \dots, \nabla f^{i,m}(x) \right), \quad \nabla^2 f^i(x) := \left(\nabla^2 f^{i,1}(x), \nabla^2 f^{i,2}(x), \dots, \nabla^2 f^{i,m}(x) \right),$$

where, for $r = 1, \dots, m$, each $\nabla f^{i,r}(x)$ and $\nabla^2 f^{i,r}(x)$ is a $1 \times n$ and an $n \times n$ matrix, respectively, and hence $\nabla f^i(x)$ and $\nabla^2 f^i(x)$ are an $m \times n$ and an $mn \times n$ matrix, respectively.

3. Rate of Convergence for TRM-SOP

In this section, we show that TRM-SOP attains a linear convergence rate. To this end, we first recall Assumptions 4.1–4.4 from (Ghosh et al. 2025b). We then introduce an additional assumption and provide the required lemmas and theorems.

ASSUMPTION 1. *The level set $\mathcal{L}_0 := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : F(x) \preceq_K^l F(x_0)\}$ is bounded.*

ASSUMPTION 2. *The function f^i is bounded below for each $i \in [p]$.*

ASSUMPTION 3. *There exists a $\mathcal{K}_1 > 0$ such that for each $i \in [p]$,*

$$\|\nabla f^i(x)\| \leq \mathcal{K}_1 \text{ for all } x \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

ASSUMPTION 4. *There exists a $\mathcal{K}_2 > 0$ such that for each $i \in [p]$,*

$$\|\nabla^2 f^i(x)\| \leq \mathcal{K}_2 \text{ for all } x \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

ASSUMPTION 5. *There exists a set $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ such that the sequence $\{x_k\}$ generated by the algorithm remains in U . Moreover, there exists a constant vector $A = (A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m)$, with $A_i \in \mathbb{R}$, in \mathbb{R}^m whose every coordinate is a positive real number, such that for all $x \in U$ and $s \in \mathbb{R}^n$*

$$A\|s\|^2 \preceq_K s^\top \nabla^2 f^i(x) s, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, p, \quad (6)$$

where $s^\top \nabla^2 f^i(x) s := (s^\top \nabla^2 f^{i,1}(x_k) s, s^\top \nabla^2 f^{i,2}(x_k) s, \dots, s^\top \nabla^2 f^{i,m}(x_k) s)^\top$

LEMMA 2. *Assume that for any $\epsilon', \delta > 0$,*

$$\|\nabla^2 f^i(x) - \nabla^2 f^i(y)\|_2 < \epsilon' \quad \text{whenever } \|x - y\| < \delta,$$

for all $i = 1, \dots, p$. Then, for all x, y with $\|x - y\| < \delta$,

$$\|\nabla f^i(y) - (\nabla f^i(x) + \nabla^2 f^i(x)^\top (y - x))\| \leq \sqrt{m} \epsilon' \|y - x\|,$$

and

$$\left\| f^i(y) - \left(f^i(x)^\top (y - x) + \frac{1}{2} (y - x)^\top \nabla f^i(x) (y - x) \right) \right\| \leq \frac{\sqrt{m} \epsilon'}{2} \|y - x\|^2,$$

for all $i = 1, \dots, p$.

Proof It is straightforward following the proof of Lemma 5 in (Carrizo et al. 2016).

Note 3.1 *In the next lemma, we use the fact that $T_A := -\Delta_{-K}(-A) > 0$, which follows from the inclusion $0 \preceq_K A$ by applying Definition 1 (viii) and Definition 1 (iii).*

The next lemma bounds $|\theta(x_k)|$ in terms of step size $\|s_k\|$.

LEMMA 3. *Let $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$. Additionally, let T_A be as in Note 3.1, where A satisfies Assumption 5. Then, for the solution of subproblem (4), we have*

$$\frac{T_A}{2} \|s_k\|^2 \leq |\theta(x_k)|.$$

Proof The Lagrangian of problem (4) can be written as

$$L((t_1, s_k), (\lambda^1, \lambda^2, \lambda^3)) := t_1 + \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \left(\Delta_{-K}(\nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s_k + \frac{1}{2} s_k^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) s_k) - t_1 \right) \\ + \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^2 \left(\Delta_{-K}(\nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s_k) - t_1 \right) + \lambda^3 \left(\frac{\|s_k\|^2}{2} - \frac{\Omega_k^2}{2} \right),$$

for all $j \in [\omega_k]$, where $\lambda^1 = (\lambda_1^1, \dots, \lambda_{\omega_k}^1)$, $\lambda^2 = (\lambda_1^2, \dots, \lambda_{\omega_k}^2) \in \mathbb{R}^{\omega_k}$, and $\lambda^3 \in \mathbb{R}$. The Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions for (4) are given by

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \Delta_{-K}((\nabla f^{a_{j,r}^k}(x_k)^\top s_k)_{r \in [m]} + (s_k^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_{j,r}^k}(x_k) s_k)_{r \in [m]}) \\ + \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^2 \Delta_{-K}((\nabla f^{a_{j,r}^k}(x_k)^\top s_k)_{r \in [m]}) + \lambda^3 s_k = 0, \quad \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 = 1, \quad \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^2 = 1, \quad \lambda_j^1, \lambda_j^2 \geq 0, \\ \Delta_{-K}((\nabla f^{a_{j,r}^k}(x_k)^\top s_k + \frac{1}{2} s_k^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_{j,r}^k}(x_k) s_k)_{r \in [m]}) - t_1 \leq 0, \tag{7}$$

$$\Delta_{-K}((\nabla f^{a_{j,r}^k}(x_k)^\top s_k)_{r \in [m]}) - t_1 \leq 0, \tag{8}$$

$$\lambda_j^1 (\Delta_{-K}((\nabla f^{a_{j,r}^k}(x_k)^\top s_k + \frac{1}{2} s_k^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_{j,r}^k}(x_k) s_k)_{r \in [m]}) - t_1) = 0, \tag{9}$$

$$\lambda_j^2 (\Delta_{-K}((\nabla f^{a_{j,r}^k}(x_k)^\top s_k)_{r \in [m]}) - t_1) = 0, \tag{10}$$

$$\frac{\|s_k\|^2}{2} \leq \frac{\Omega_k^2}{2}, \quad \lambda^3 \left(\frac{\|s_k\|^2}{2} - \frac{\Omega_k^2}{2} \right) = 0, \quad \lambda^3 \geq 0. \tag{11}$$

Note that when constraints (7) and (8) are active, they vanish from the Lagrangian. When they are inactive, i.e., $\|s_k\| < \Omega_k$, then complementary slackness gives

$$L((t_1, s_k), (\lambda^1, \lambda^2)) = t_1.$$

Let (t_k^*, s_k^*) denote an optimal solution of (4). Then s_k^* satisfies

$$\left[\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k) \right] = - \left[\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) \right]^\top s_k^*, \quad \text{and } t_k^* = \Delta_{-K} \left(- \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} s_k^{*\top} \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) s_k^* \right), \tag{12}$$

where

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla f^{a_j^k}(x) := \left(\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla f^{a_{j,1}^k}(x), \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla f^{a_{j,2}^k}(x), \dots, \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla f^{a_{j,m}^k}(x) \right),$$

and

$$\left[\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x) \right]^\top s := \left(\left[\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla^2 f^{a_{j,1}^k}(x) \right]^\top s, \left[\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla^2 f^{a_{j,2}^k}(x) \right]^\top s, \right. \\ \left. \dots, \left[\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla^2 f^{a_{j,m}^k}(x) \right]^\top s \right).$$

Substituting t_k^* and s_k^* , the Lagrangian evaluates to

$$L((t_1, s_k), (\lambda^1, \lambda^2)) = \Delta_{-K} \left(-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} s_k^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) s_k \right) = t_k.$$

Finally, using Assumption 5, we obtain

$$|\theta(x_k)| = -\theta(x_k) = -t_k = -\Delta_{-K} \left(-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} s_k^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) s_k \right) \geq -\frac{\Delta_{-K}(-A)}{2} \|s_k\|^2 = \frac{T_A}{2} \|s_k\|^2.$$

This completes the proof.

The next lemma shows that the stationarity measure (solution of subproblem (4)) is upper-bounded in terms of the norm squared of part of the subproblem Lagrangian gradient (the gradients of \tilde{f}^{a^k}).

LEMMA 4. *Let $x \in U$. Additionally, let T_A be as in Note 3.1, where A satisfies Assumption 5. Then, for every set of nonnegative weights $\lambda_j \geq 0$, $j = 1, \dots, \omega_k$, with $\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j = 1$, the solution of the subproblem (4) satisfies*

$$|\theta(x_k)| \leq \frac{1}{2T_A} \left\| \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j \nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k) \right\|^2. \quad (13)$$

Proof Consider the dual formulation of the subproblem (4):

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{\lambda_j^1, \lambda_j^2, \lambda_j^3 \geq 0} \inf_{(t, s)} \left\{ t + \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 (\Delta_{-K} (\nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s + \frac{1}{2} s^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) s)) - t \right\} + \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^2 (\Delta_{-K} (\nabla f^{a_j^k} \\ & (x_k)^\top s_k) - t) + \lambda_j^3 \left(\frac{\|s\|^2}{2} - \frac{\Omega_k^2}{2} \right) \right\} \text{ for all } j \in [\omega_k], \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

with $\lambda^1 = (\lambda_1^1, \lambda_2^1, \lambda_3^1, \dots, \lambda_{\omega_k}^1) \in \mathbb{R}^{\omega_k}$, $\lambda^2 = (\lambda_1^2, \lambda_2^2, \lambda_3^2, \dots, \lambda_{\omega_k}^2) \in \mathbb{R}^{\omega_k}$ and $\lambda^3 \in \mathbb{R}$. Adding the normalization constraint $\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 = 1$ and noting that $\lambda_j^1, \lambda^3 \geq 0$, we can focus on

$$\theta(x_k) \geq \sup_{\substack{\lambda_j^1 \geq 0, \\ \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 = 1}} \inf_s \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 (\Delta_{-K} (\nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s + \frac{1}{2} s^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) s)) + \lambda^3 \left(\frac{\|s\|^2}{2} - \frac{\Omega_k^2}{2} \right) \right\}.$$

By choosing $s = 0$ for the second term, the supremum is attained at $\lambda^3 = 0$, giving

$$\theta(x_k) \geq \sup_{\substack{\lambda_j^1 \geq 0, \\ \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 = 1}} \inf_s \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \left(\Delta_{-K} (\nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s + \frac{1}{2} s^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) s) \right).$$

Using Assumption 5, the inequality reduces to

$$\theta(x_k) \geq \sup_{\substack{\lambda_j^1 \geq 0, \\ \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 = 1}} \inf_s \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \left(\Delta_{-K} (\nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s + \frac{1}{2} \|s\|^2 A) \right).$$

By the trial-and-error approach, we find that the infimum occurs at

$$s = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)}{\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \Delta_{-K}(-A)}.$$

Substituting this s yields

$$-\theta(x_k) \leq \sup_{\substack{\lambda_j^1 \geq 0, \\ \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 = 1}} - \frac{\left\| \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k) \right\|^2}{2 \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \Delta_{-K}(-A)} = - \frac{\left\| \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j^1 \nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k) \right\|^2}{2 \Delta_{-K}(-A)}.$$

Finally, taking $\theta(x) \leq 0$ and with $\lambda_j^1 = \lambda_j$, we obtain

$$|\theta(x_k)| \leq \frac{1}{2T_A} \left\| \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j \nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k) \right\|^2, \quad \lambda_j \geq 0, j = 1, \dots, \omega_k, \text{ such that } \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \lambda_j = 1.$$

This concludes the proof.

Next, we establish an auxiliary lemma showing that, for sufficiently small δ and ϵ' , the step sizes decay multiplicatively, which indicates the convergence rate given in the subsequent theorem.

LEMMA 5. Let $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$, and let \widehat{x} with $\widehat{x}_+ = \widehat{x} + s(\widehat{x})$. Let A and $r, \delta, \epsilon' > 0$ are such that:

- (a) $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ and $0 \prec_K A$ satisfies Assumption 5;
- (b) $\mathcal{B}(\widehat{x}, r) \subseteq U$;
- (c) $\|f^i(x) - f^i(y)\| \leq \epsilon'$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{B}(\widehat{x}, r)$ with $\|x - y\| < \delta$;
- (d) $\|s(\widehat{x}_+)\| < \min\{\delta, r\}$.

Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\|s(\widehat{x}_+)\| \leq \frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{T_A} \|\widehat{s}\|.$$

Proof Let $\widehat{\lambda}_j^1, \widehat{\lambda}_j^2, \widehat{\lambda} > 0, j = 1(1)\omega_k$, denote the multipliers corresponding to the subproblem (4) at $x = \widehat{x}$. Since the trust-region constraint is inactive, all associated multipliers vanish except $\widehat{\lambda}_j^1$, which satisfy $\sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \widehat{\lambda}_j^1 = 1$. From Lemma 4, we obtain (13). Now, we define

$$\mathcal{G}(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \widehat{\lambda}_j^1 f^{a_j^k}(x_k).$$

Then, we have

$$\nabla \mathcal{G}(\widehat{x}_+) = \nabla \mathcal{G}(\widehat{x} + s(\widehat{x})) = \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \widehat{\lambda}_j^1 \nabla f^{a_j^k}(\widehat{x} + s(\widehat{x})), \text{ and } \nabla^2 \mathcal{G}(\widehat{x}_+) = \sum_{j=1}^{\omega_k} \widehat{\lambda}_j^1 \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(\widehat{x}).$$

From (12) with $x_k = \widehat{x}$, we obtain

$$\nabla \mathcal{G}(\widehat{x}) = -\nabla^2 \mathcal{G}(\widehat{x})^\top s(\widehat{x}) = -\nabla^2 \mathcal{G}(\widehat{x})^\top \widehat{s}. \tag{15}$$

Since $\nabla^2 \mathcal{G}$ is a convex combination of the $\nabla^2 f^{a_j}$, it is uniformly continuous. Thus, Lemma 2 gives

$$\|\nabla \mathcal{G}(\widehat{x} + \widehat{s}) - (\nabla \mathcal{G}(\widehat{x}) + \nabla^2 \mathcal{G}(\widehat{x}))\| \leq \sqrt{m} \epsilon' \|\widehat{s}\|; \text{ thus by (15), } \|\nabla \mathcal{G}(\widehat{x}_+)\| \leq \sqrt{m} \epsilon' \|\widehat{s}\|.$$

Finally, using Lemmas 3 and 4, we have

$$\frac{T_A}{2} \|\widehat{s}_+\|^2 \leq |\theta(\widehat{x}_+)| \leq \frac{m\epsilon'^2 \|\widehat{s}\|^2}{2T_A}, \text{ which yields } \|\widehat{s}_+\| \leq \frac{\sqrt{m} \epsilon'}{T_A} \|\widehat{s}\|.$$

Next, the following result ensures that the sequence generated by the algorithm converges to a K -critical point.

THEOREM 1. *Let $\{x_k\}$ be the sequence generated by Algorithm 1 in (Ghosh et al. 2025b), and let $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$, A , r , δ , $\epsilon' > 0$ satisfy:*

- (a) $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ and $0 \prec_K A$ satisfies Assumption 5;
- (b) $\|\nabla^2 f^i(x) - \nabla^2 f^i(y)\| \leq \epsilon'$ for all $x, y \in U$ with $\|x - y\| < \delta$;
- (c) $\frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{T_A} < 1 - \eta_2$, where η_2 is the threshold for a very successful iteration in Algorithm 1;
- (d) $\mathcal{B}(x_0, r) \subseteq U$;
- (e) $\|s(x_0)\| \leq \min \left\{ \delta, r \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{T_A} \right) \right\}$.

Then the following statements hold for all $k \geq 0$:

- (i) $\|x_k - x_0\| \leq \|s(x_0)\| \frac{1 - \left(\frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{T_A}\right)^k}{1 - \frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{T_A}}$;
- (ii) $\|s(x_k)\| \leq \|s(x_0)\| \left(\frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{T_A}\right)^k$;
- (iii) $\Omega_{k+1} \geq \Omega_k$;
- (iv) $\|s(x_{k+1})\| \leq \|s(x_k)\| \frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{T_A}$.

Consequently, the sequence $\{x_k\}$ converges to a K -critical point.

Proof See Appendix B.

Lastly, we show that TRM-SOP achieves a linear rate.

THEOREM 2. *Under the assumptions of Theorem 1, let*

$$\tau_k = \frac{\sqrt{m} \epsilon'}{T_A}$$

and fix $\xi \in (0, \frac{1}{3})$. Then there exists k_0 such that for all $k \geq k_0$, $\tau_k < \xi$, and

$$\|x^* - x_{k+1}\| \leq \frac{\tau_k}{1 - 2\tau_k} \|x^* - x_k\| \leq \frac{\xi}{1 - 2\xi} \|x^* - x_k\|,$$

where x^* is an accumulation point of $\{x_k\}$ and a critical point.

Proof From Theorem 1, we have

$$\|s_k\| \leq \|s_0\| \left(\frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{T_A}\right)^k.$$

Since $\frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{T_A} < 1$, there exists k_0 such that for all $k \geq k_0$, $\tau_k < \xi$. Applying Lemma 5, we obtain

$$\|s_{k+1}\| \leq \frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{T_A} \|s_k\|. \tag{16}$$

For any $i > k \geq k_0$,

$$\|x_i - x_{k+1}\| \leq \sum_{j=k+2}^i \|x_j - x_{j-1}\| \leq \sum_{j=k+2}^i \|s_{j-1}\|, \text{ so } \|x^* - x_{k+1}\| \leq \sum_{j=k+1}^{\infty} \|s_j\| \text{ as } i \rightarrow \infty.$$

Using (16) leads to

$$\|x^* - x_{k+1}\| \leq \frac{\tau_k}{1 - \tau_k} \|s_k\|. \quad (17)$$

Hence,

$$\|x^* - x_k\| \geq \|x_{k+1} - x_k\| - \|x^* - x_{k+1}\| \geq \|s_k\| - \frac{\tau_k}{1 - \tau_k} \|s_k\| = \frac{1 - 2\tau_k}{1 - \tau_k} \|s_k\|. \quad (18)$$

From (18), it follows that

$$\|s_k\| \leq \|x^* - x_k\| \frac{1 - \tau_k}{1 - 2\tau_k}.$$

Combining (17) and (18) yields

$$\|x^* - x_{k+1}\| \leq \frac{\tau_k}{1 - 2\tau_k} \|x^* - x_k\|.$$

Since $\varphi(t) = \frac{t}{1-2t}$ is increasing for $t \in (0, \frac{1}{3})$, this establishes the linear convergence of TRM-SOP.

4. Iteration-Complexity for TRM-SOP

Besides convergence rate, iteration complexity also reflects the speed of convergence of an algorithm. Therefore, in this section, we derive an iteration bound for TRM-SOP.

First, we show that for non-critical point, the trust-region radius cannot vanish, and Ω_k is bounded below, i.e., x_k cannot be non-critical while $\Omega_k \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

LEMMA 6. *Under Assumption 4.2 in (Ghosh et al. 2025b), suppose there exists $\sigma > 0$ such that*

$$0 < \sigma < \frac{|\Delta_{-K}(\nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s_k)|}{\|s_k\|}$$

for every iteration $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and every $j \in [\omega_k]$. Then, there exists a constant $\Omega_{\min} > 0$ such that

$$\Omega_k > \Omega_{\min} \quad \forall k.$$

Proof We argue this by contradiction. Assume that there exists a subsequence $\{\Omega_{k_i}\}$ with $\Omega_{k_i} \rightarrow 0$, i.e., for any $\epsilon > 0$, there exists k_0 with $\Omega_{k_i} < \epsilon$ for all $i \geq k_0$. Let k_0 be the first such index, so $\Omega_{k_0} < \Omega_{k_0-1}$.

By the trust-region update rule (Case 3, Step 10 of Algorithm 1 in (Ghosh et al. 2025b)), we have $\Omega_{k_0} \geq \gamma_1 \Omega_{k_0-1}$ with $\gamma_1 \in (0, 1)$. Set

$$\epsilon = \frac{\gamma_1 \sigma \beta (1 - \eta_2)}{2\mathcal{K}_1},$$

where β is from (4.9) and \mathcal{K}_1 is from Assumption 4.2. Then, for each $j \in [\omega_{k_0-1}]$,

$$\Omega_{k_0-1} \leq \frac{\Omega_{k_0}}{\gamma_1} < \frac{\epsilon}{\gamma_1} = \frac{\sigma \beta (1 - \eta_2)}{2\mathcal{K}_1} \leq \frac{\beta (1 - \eta_2)}{2\mathcal{K}_1} \frac{|\Delta_{-K}(\nabla f^{a_j^{k_0-1}}(x_{k_0-1})^\top s_{k_0-1})|}{\|s_{k_0-1}\|},$$

where the last inequality uses the lemma's statement. By Theorem 7 in (Ghosh et al. 2025b), iteration $k_0 - 1$ is very successful, implying $\Omega_{k_0-1} \leq \Omega_{k_0}$, which contradicts our initial assumption $\Omega_{k_0} < \Omega_{k_0-1}$. Thus, no such subsequence can exist, and we must have

$$\Omega_k > \frac{\gamma_1 \sigma \beta (1 - \eta_2)}{2\mathcal{K}_1} = \Omega_{\min}, \quad \forall k. \quad (19)$$

This completes the proof.

The next lemma shows that the number of successful iterations, starting from the iteration when the radius is first reduced, is bounded.

THEOREM 3. *Let k_0 be the index of the first iteration at which Ω_k decreases (its existence follows from Lemma 6). Fix any $\epsilon \in (0, 1)$ and assume that*

$$\frac{\Delta_{-K}(\nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s_k)}{\|s_k\|} \geq \epsilon.$$

Let $k_\epsilon > k_0$ be the first iteration such that $|\theta(x_k)| < \epsilon$. Then, starting from iteration k_0 , Algorithm 1 requires at most $|S(k_0, k_\epsilon)|$ successful iterations to achieve the condition $|\theta(x_k)| < \epsilon$, where

$$|S(k_0, k_\epsilon)| \leq \frac{\Delta_{-K}(f^{a_j^k}(x_{k_0}) - f^{a_j^k}(x_{k_\epsilon}))}{L_1} \epsilon^{-2} \leq \frac{\sqrt{m} \Sigma}{L_1} \epsilon^{-2}.$$

Here,

$$L_1 = (\lambda \eta_1 + (1 - \lambda) \eta_2) \epsilon^2 \beta \frac{1}{2} \min \left\{ \frac{1}{\mathcal{K}_2}, \frac{\gamma_1 \beta (1 - \eta_2)}{2\mathcal{K}_1} \right\}, \quad 0 < \lambda < 1,$$

and

$$\Sigma = \max_{i \in [p]} \Delta_{-K}(f^i(x_0) - \inf_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} f^i(x)) \text{ is the optimality gap.}$$

Proof For each successful iteration, there exists an index $l \in [\omega_k]$ such that

$$\eta_1 \leq \rho_k^{a_l^k} < \eta_2 \text{ implies } \rho_k^{a_l^k} = \lambda \eta_1 + (1 - \lambda) \eta_2, \quad 0 < \lambda < 1.$$

Using this identity together with the definition of $\rho_k^{a_l^k}$ given in (Ghosh et al. 2025b), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{-K}(f^{a_j^l}(x_{k_0}) - f^{a_j^l}(x_{k_\epsilon})) &\geq \sum_{l=0, l \in \mathcal{S}}^{k_\epsilon-1} \left(\Delta_{-K}(f^{a_j^l}(x_l)) - \Delta_{-K}(f^{a_j^l}(x_{l+1})) \right) \\ &\geq \sum_{l=0, l \in \mathcal{S}}^{k_\epsilon-1} (\lambda \eta_1 + (1 - \lambda) \eta_2) \epsilon \beta \frac{1}{2} \min \left\{ \frac{\epsilon}{\mathcal{K}_2}, \Omega_{\min} \right\} \\ &\geq |S(k_0, k_\epsilon)| (\lambda \eta_1 + (1 - \lambda) \eta_2) \epsilon^2 \beta \frac{1}{2} \min \left\{ \frac{1}{\mathcal{K}_2}, \frac{\gamma \beta (1 - \eta_2)}{2\mathcal{K}_1} \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

where $|S(k_0, k_\epsilon)|$ denotes the number of successful iterations from k_0 up to k_ϵ . Since the left-hand side is bounded by the optimality gap, the stated upper bound follows. This completes the proof.

Note 4.1 Proceeding in the same manner as in the proof of Theorem 3, one can show that Algorithm 1 requires at most $|\mathcal{VS}(k_0, k_\epsilon)|$ very successful iterations. In particular,

$$|\mathcal{VS}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| \leq \frac{\Delta_{-K} \left(f^{a_j^k}(x_{k_0}) - f^{a_j^k}(x_{k_\epsilon}) \right)}{L_2} \epsilon^{-2} \leq \frac{\sqrt{m} \Sigma}{L_2} \epsilon^{-2},$$

where

$$L_2 = \eta_2 \epsilon^2 \beta \frac{1}{2} \min \left\{ \frac{1}{\mathcal{K}_2}, \frac{\gamma_1 \beta (1 - \eta_2)}{2\mathcal{K}_1} \right\}.$$

The next theorem shows that, starting from the iteration when the radius is first reduced, the number of unsuccessful iterations is bounded in terms of the number of successful iterations.

THEOREM 4. Under the assumptions of Theorem 3, in order to reach the condition $|\theta(x_k)| < \epsilon$, beginning from iteration k_0 , Algorithm 1 requires at most $|\mathcal{N}(k_0, k_\epsilon)|$ non-successful iterations, where

$$|\mathcal{N}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| \leq -\log_{\gamma_2}(\gamma_3) |\mathcal{S}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| + \log_{\gamma_2} \left(\frac{\gamma_1 C_3 e}{\Omega_{k_0}} \right) - \log_{\gamma_2}(e) \epsilon^{-1}.$$

Proof For each successful iteration $k \in \mathcal{S}$, the update rule guarantees that

$$\Omega_{k+1} \leq \gamma_3 \Omega_k, \gamma_3 \in (\gamma_2, 1],$$

and for each unsuccessful iteration $k \in \mathcal{N}$,

$$\Omega_{k+1} \leq \gamma_2 \Omega_k.$$

By induction, this yields

$$\Omega_{k_\epsilon} \leq \gamma_2^{|\mathcal{N}(k_0, k_\epsilon)|} \gamma_3^{|\mathcal{S}(k_0, k_\epsilon)|} \Omega_{k_0}.$$

Taking logarithms and using the fact that $\log(\gamma_2) < 0$ and $\log(\gamma_3) < 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\Omega_{k_\epsilon}) &\leq \log(\Omega_{k_0}) + |\mathcal{N}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| \log(\gamma_2) + |\mathcal{S}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| \log(\gamma_3), \\ \implies \frac{\log(\Omega_{k_\epsilon})}{\log(\gamma_2)} &\geq \frac{\log(\Omega_{k_0})}{\log(\gamma_2)} + |\mathcal{N}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| + \frac{\log(\gamma_3)}{\log(\gamma_2)} |\mathcal{S}(k_0, k_\epsilon)|. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

From Lemma 6, $\Omega_k \geq \gamma_1 C_3 \epsilon$ for all $k = k_0, \dots, k_\epsilon - 1$, where $C_3 = \frac{\beta(1 - \eta_2)}{2\mathcal{K}_1}$. Since $\log(\gamma_2) < 0$,

$$\frac{\log(\Omega_{k_\epsilon})}{\log(\gamma_2)} \leq \frac{\log(\gamma_1 C_3)}{\log(\gamma_2)} + \frac{\log(\epsilon)}{\log(\gamma_2)}. \quad (21)$$

Combining (20) and (21) gives

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{N}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| &\leq -\frac{\log(\gamma_3)}{\log(\gamma_2)} |\mathcal{S}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| - \frac{\log(\Omega_{k_0})}{\log(\gamma_2)} + \frac{\log(\gamma_1 C_3)}{\log(\gamma_2)} + \frac{\log(\epsilon)}{\log(\gamma_2)} \\ &= -\log_{\gamma_2}(\gamma_3) |\mathcal{S}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| + \log_{\gamma_2} \left(\frac{\gamma_1 C_3}{\Omega_{k_0}} \right) - \frac{\log(\epsilon^{-1})}{\log(\gamma_2)} \\ &\leq -\log_{\gamma_2}(\gamma_3) |\mathcal{S}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| + \log_{\gamma_2} \left(\frac{\gamma_1 C_3 e}{\Omega_{k_0}} \right) - \log_{\gamma_2}(e) \epsilon^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the upper bound $|\mathcal{S}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| \leq \frac{\sqrt{m}\Sigma}{L_1} \epsilon^{-2}$ from Theorem 3 gives the desired result.

REMARK 1. From Theorem 4, we also obtain an upper bound on k_0 . Indeed, as shown in the proof of Theorem 4, there are no unsuccessful iterations prior to k_0 ; that is, $\mathcal{N}(k_0, k_\epsilon) = \emptyset$. Consequently,

$$\begin{aligned} k_0 &\leq |\mathcal{V}\mathcal{S}(k_0, k_\epsilon)| + (1 - \log_{\gamma_2}(\gamma_3)) |S(k_0, k_\epsilon)| \\ &= \sqrt{m} \Sigma \epsilon^{-2} \left(\frac{1 - \log_{\gamma_2}(\gamma_3)}{L_1} + \frac{1}{L_2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, from Theorem 3, Note 4.1, Theorem 4, and Remark 1, we get that the overall number of iterations required to ensure $|\theta(x_k)| < \epsilon$ is bounded by

$$O\left(1 + 2\sqrt{m} \Sigma \epsilon^{-2} \left(\frac{1 - \log_{\gamma_2}(\gamma_3)}{L_1} + \frac{1}{L_2} \right) + \log_{\gamma_2} \left(\frac{\gamma_1 C_3 e}{\Omega_{k_0}} \right) - \log_{\gamma_2}(e) \epsilon^{-1} \right).$$

Therefore, we get that TRM-SOP achieves a worst-case complexity bound of $O(\epsilon^{-2})$. This bound is consistent with the classical worst-case complexity bound for trust-region methods for nonconvex scalar optimization problems Grapiglia et al. (2015).

Finally, note that tighter bounds of $O(\epsilon^{-1.5})$ can be found in the literature for some trust-region methods for scalar optimization (e.g., (Nesterov and Polyak 2006, Curtis et al. 2017, Cartis et al. 2012)); however, they cannot be directly compared to our TRM-SOP, as their algorithmic frameworks fundamentally differ from ours. In particular, these methods employ the TRACE framework (see Section 2.2 in Curtis et al. (2017)), which combines a contraction-expansion mechanism with two trust-region radii and a regularization parameter to guarantee a lower bound on the step size and achieve tighter complexity. In contrast, our TRM-SOP is an extension of the classical trust-region method to set optimization problems. Investigating tighter bounds for set optimization remains an interesting direction for future research.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we have analyzed the convergence rate and iteration complexity of TRM-SOP. First, we have related the subproblem solution $|\theta(x)|$ to the step size $\|s\|$ and derived an upper bound in Subproblem (4), showing that the method achieves a linear convergence rate. Next, we have analyzed iteration complexity by bounding the trust-region radius, counting very successful and successful iterations, and expressing unsuccessful iterations in terms of successful ones. Finally, we have shown that TRM-SOP requires $O(\sqrt{m} \Sigma \epsilon^{-2})$ iterations to reach the K -critical point. In future work, this study can be extended by conducting a detailed analysis of the computational complexity associated with function and gradient evaluations, as well as the time required to reach a K -critical point. Additionally, the linear convergence rate and the $O(\epsilon^{-2})$ iteration bound established in this paper can be further investigated and validated through numerical experiments.

References

- Ansari QH, Kobis E, & Sharma PK (2018) Characterizations of set relations with respect to variable domination structures via oriented distance function. *Optimization* 67(9):1389-1407.
- Bouza G, Quintana E, & Tammer C (2021) A steepest descent method for set optimization problems with set-valued mappings of finite cardinality. *Journal of optimization theory and applications* 190(3):711-743.
- Curtis FE, Robinson DP & Samadi M (2017) A trust region algorithm with a worst-case iteration complexity of $O(\epsilon^{-\frac{3}{2}})$ for nonconvex optimization. *Mathematical Programming* 162(1):1-32.
- Nesterov Y, & Polyak BT (2006) Cubic regularization of Newton's method and its global performance. *Mathematical Programming* 108(1):177-205.

- Cartis C, Gould, NIM, Toint PhL (2011) Adaptive cubic regularisation methods for unconstrained optimization part II: worst-case function-evaluation complexity. *Mathematical Programming* 130(2):295–319.
- Cartis C, Gould NIM, & Toint PL (2012) Complexity bounds for second-order optimality in unconstrained optimization. *Journal of Complexity* 28(1):93-108.
- Eichfelder G, Niebling J, & Rocktäschel S (2020) An algorithmic approach to multiobjective optimization with decision uncertainty. *Journal of Global Optimization* 77(1):3-25.
- Garmanjani R (2023) Complexity bound of trust-region methods for convex smooth unconstrained multiobjective optimization. *Optimization Letters* 17(5): 1161–1179.
- Custódio AL, Diouane Y, Garmanjani R & Riccietti E (2021) Worst-Case Complexity Bounds of Directional Direct-Search Methods for Multiobjective Optimization. *Journal of Optimization theory and Application* 188(1):73–93
- Villacorta KDV, Oliveira PR, Soubeyran A (2014) A trust-region method for unconstrained multiobjective problems with applications in satisficing processes. *Journal of Optimization theory and Applications* 160(3):865–889.
- Shani L, Efroni Y, & Mannor S (2020) Adaptive trust region policy optimization: Global convergence and faster rates for regularized MDPs. *In Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence* 34(4): 5668–5675.
- Xia Yu, Wu Hao (2024) Convergence Rate of Greedy SR1 With Trust Region Method. *Highlights in Science, Engineering and Technology* Vol. 115(2024): 468–481.
- Shen Z, Zhou P, Fang C. & Ribeiro A (2020) A stochastic trust region method for non-convex minimization. *arXiv:1903.01540*.
- Chen Z, Milzarek A, Wen Z (2023) A Trust-Region Method for Nonsmooth Nonconvex Optimization. *Journal of Computational Mathematics* 41(4) :683–716.
- Fan J (2006) Convergence rate of the trust region method for nonlinear equations under local error bound condition. *Computational Optimization and Applications* 34(2):215-227.
- Liu S, & Vicente LN (2023) Convergence rates of the stochastic alternating algorithm for bi-objective optimization. *Journal of Optimization Theory and Applications* 198(1):165-186.
- Löhne A (2025) A solution method for arbitrary polyhedral convex set optimization problems. *SIAM Journal on Optimization* 35(1):330-346.
- Bisui N K, & Panda G (2025) A trust-region scheme for constrained multi-objective optimization problems with superlinear convergence property. *Optimization Methods and Software* 40(1):24-64.
- Carrizo GA, Lotito PA, & Maciel MC. (2016) Trust region globalization strategy for the nonconvex unconstrained multiobjective optimization problem. *Mathematical Programming* 159(1):339-369.
- Ghosh D, Ansari QH, & Zhao X (2024) Newton Method for set optimization problems with set-valued mapping of finitely many vector-valued functions. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.19636*.
- Ghosh D, Anshika, Yao JC, & Zhao X (2025) Quasi-Newton Method for Set Optimization Problems with Set-Valued Mapping Given by Finitely Many Vector-Valued Functions. *Numerical Functional Analysis and Optimization* 1-41.
- Kumar K, Ghosh D, Yao JC, & Zhao X (2025) Nonlinear conjugate gradient methods for unconstrained set optimization problems whose objective functions have finite cardinality. *Optimization* 74(15):3839-3878.
- Garmanjani R, Júdice D, & Vicente LN. (2016) Trust-region methods without using derivatives: worst case complexity and the nonsmooth case. *SIAM Journal on Optimization* 26(4):1987-2011.
- Mastrogiacomo E, & Rocca M (2021) Set optimization of set-valued risk measures. *Annals of Operations Research* 296(1):291-314.
- Hamel AH, & Heyde F (2010) Duality for set-valued measures of risk. *SIAM Journal on Financial Mathematics* 1(1):66-95.
- Hamel, AH, & Löhne, A (2018) A set optimization approach to zero-sum matrix games with multi-dimensional payoffs. *Mathematical Methods of Operations Research* 88(3):369-397.
- Hamel, AH, & Visetti D (2020) The value functions approach and Hopf-Lax formula for multiobjective costs via set optimization. *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications* 483(1):123605.

- Jahn J (2015) A derivative-free descent method in set optimization. *Computational Optimization and Applications* 60(2):393–411.
- Günther C, Köbis E, & Popovici N (2019) Computing minimal elements of finite families of sets wrt preorder relations in set optimization. *Journal of applied and numerical optimization* 1(2): 131-144.
- Ghosh S, Ghosh D, Tammer C, Zhao X (2025) Trust-region method for optimization of set-valued maps given by finitely many functions. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2509.07836>
- Gratton S, Sartenaer A, Toint PhL (2008) Recursive trust-region methods for multiscale nonlinear optimization. *SIAM Journal on Optimization* 19(1):414–444.
- Grapiglia GN, Yuan, J, Yuan Y (2015) On the convergence and worst-case complexity of trust-region and regularization methods for unconstrained optimization. *Mathematical Programming* 152(1):491–520.
- Grapiglia GN, Yuan, J, Yuan Y (2016) On the worst-case complexity of nonlinear stepsize control algorithms for convex unconstrained optimization. *Optimization Methods and Software* 31(3):591–604.
- Garmanjani R (2022) A note on the worst-case complexity of nonlinear stepsize control methods for convex smooth unconstrained optimization. *Optimization* 71(6):1709–1719.
- Zaffaroni, A.: Degrees of efficiency and degrees of minimality. *SIAM J. Control Optim.* 42(3), 1071–1086, (2003)

Appendix A: TRM-SOP for solving (SOP_K^l)

Algorithm 1 Trust-region algorithm for solving (SOP_K^l)

1: *Input and initialization*

Provide the functions $f^i : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$, of the problem (SOP_K^l) . Choose an initial point x_0 , an initial trust-region radius Ω_0 , a maximum allowed trust-region radius Ω_{\max} , a tolerance value ε for stopping criterion, threshold parameters $\eta_1, \eta_2 \in (0, 1)$ with $\eta_1 < \eta_2$, and fractions $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in (0, 1)$ to shrink the trust-region radius. Set the iteration counter $k := 0$.

2: *Computation of minimal elements*

Compute $M_k := \text{Min}(F(x_k), K) = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{\omega_k}\}$.
 Compute the partition set $P_k := I_{r_1} \times I_{r_2} \times \dots \times I_{r_{\omega_k}}$.
 Find $p_k := |P_k|$ and $\omega_k := |\text{Min}(F(x_k), K)|$.

3: *Choice of an 'a^k' from P_k*

Select an element $a^k := (a_1^k, a_2^k, \dots, a_{\omega_k}^k) \in P_k$ such that $(a^k, s_k) \in \underset{(a,s) \in P_k \times \mathcal{B}_k}{\text{argmin}} \Theta_{x_k}(a, s)$.

4: *Model definition*

Compute the model functions $m^{a_j^k}$ for all $j \in [\omega_k]$ by the formula

$$m^{a_j^k}(s) = \nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s + \frac{1}{2} s^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) s, \|s\| \leq \Omega_k.$$

5: *Step size calculation*

Find (t_k, s_k) by solving the subproblem (4).

6: *Termination criterion*

If $|t_k| < \varepsilon$, then stop and provide x_k as an approximate K -critical point of (SOP_K^l) .
 Else, proceed to the next step.

7: *Calculation of reduction ratio*

Execute

$$\sigma_k^{a_j^k} := \frac{\Delta_{-K}(f^{a_j^k}(x_k + s_k) - f^{a_j^k}(x_k))}{\Delta_{-K}(m^{a_j^k}(0) - m^{a_j^k}(s_k))} \text{ and } \rho_k^{a_j^k} := -\sigma_k^{a_j^k} \text{ for all } j \in [\omega_k].$$

8: *Acceptance of the computed step size*

If $\rho_k^{a_j^k} \geq \eta_1$ for all $j \in [\omega_k]$, then update $x_{k+1} := x_k + s_k$.

9: *Rejection of the computed step size*

If there exists $j \in [\omega_k]$ such that $\rho_k^{a_j^k} < \eta_1$, then $x_{k+1} := x_k$.

10: *Trust-region radius update*

Choose Ω_{k+1} by the rule

$$\begin{cases} (\gamma_2 \Omega_k, \Omega_k) & \text{if } \rho_k^{a_j^k} \geq \eta_1 \forall j \in [\omega_k] \text{ and } \exists l \in [\omega_k] \text{ such that } \rho_k^{a_l^k} < \eta_2 \text{ (Successful)} \\ (\Omega_k, \infty) & \text{if } \rho_k^{a_j^k} \geq \eta_2 \forall j \in [\omega_k] \text{ (Very successful)} \\ [\gamma_1 \Omega_k, \gamma_2 \Omega_k] & \text{if } \exists l \in [\omega_k] \text{ such that } \rho_k^{a_l^k} < \eta_1 \text{ (Unsuccessful)}. \end{cases}$$

11: *Move to next iteration*

$k := k + 1$ and go to Step 2.

Appendix B: Proof of Lemma 1

Proof Parts (i) and (ii) follow using arguments analogous to those in Theorem 3 of (Ghosh et al. 2025b). Here, we focus on the remaining claims. To prove part (iii), for each $j = 1, \dots, \omega_k$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
f^{a_j^k}(x_k + s_k) - f^{a_j^k}(x_k) &\preceq_K \nabla f^{a_j^k}(x_k)^\top s_k + \frac{1}{2} s_k^\top \nabla^2 f^{a_j^k}(x_k) s_k + \frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{2} \|s_k\|^2 \\
&= m^{a_j^k}(s_k) + \frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{2} \|s_k\|^2 \\
&= \eta_2 m^{a_j^k}(s_k) + (1 - \eta_2) m^{a_j^k}(s_k) + \frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{2} \|s_k\|^2.
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Applying Lemmas 2 and 4, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
(1 - \eta_2) \Delta_{-K}(m^{a_j^k}(s_k)) + \frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{2} \|s_k\|^2 &\preceq_K (1 - \eta_2) \theta(x_k) + \frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{2} \|s_k\|^2 \\
&\preceq_K (1 - \eta_2) \frac{\Delta_{-K}(-A)}{2} \|s_k\|^2 + \frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{2} \|s_k\|^2 \\
&\preceq_K -\frac{\Delta_{-K}(-A) \|s_k\|^2}{\Delta_{-K}(-A)} \left(-\frac{\sqrt{m}\epsilon'}{\Delta_{-K}(-A)} - (1 - \eta_2) \right) \leq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, from (22) and applying Lemma 2.2(h) in (Ansari et al. 2018):

$$\begin{aligned}
f^{a_j^k}(x_k + s_k) - f^{a_j^k}(x_k) &\preceq_K \eta_2 m^{a_j^k}(s_k), \\
\Rightarrow \Delta_{-K}(f^{a_j^k}(x_k + s_k) - f^{a_j^k}(x_k)) &\leq \eta_2 \Delta_{-K}(m^{a_j^k}(s_k)), \\
\Rightarrow \frac{\Delta_{-K}(f^{a_j^k}(x_k + s_k) - f^{a_j^k}(x_k))}{-\Delta_{-K}(m^{a_j^k}(s_k))} &\leq -\eta_2, \\
\Rightarrow \rho_k^{a_j^k} &\geq \eta_2.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\Omega_{k+1} \geq \Omega_k$, and (iv) as in (Carrizo et al. 2016).

Appendix C: Plots of Rate of Convergence and Iteration Complexity (Preliminary Results)

In this section, we numerically illustrate the convergence rate behavior and iteration complexity of the TRM-SOP algorithm in Figure 1. The experimental setup is the same as in Ghosh et al. (2025b).

Figure 1 For TRM-SOP Ghosh et al. (2025b), (a) the plot of Error $|\theta(x_k)|$ vs. Iteration k illustrates the convergence-rate behavior for four problems: GGTZ8–DGO2, GGCZ18–BQT2, GGTZ2–ZDT4, and GGTZ13–Trigonometric, taken from Ghosh et al. (2025b). It shows how the error decreases as TRM-SOP progresses. The error value at each iteration is the mean error computed over the runs that reach that iteration (out of a total of 100 runs), and (b) the plot of Iteration k vs. Tolerance ϵ for the problems GGTZ9–Hill, GGTZ2–ZDT4, GGCZ15–BQT1, and GGTZ13–Trigonometric, taken from Ghosh et al. (2025b), shows the number of iterations required for the error to reach the tolerance, i.e., $|\theta(x_k)| < \epsilon$. The analytical bound $O(\epsilon^{-2})$ is shown in blue. The black line indicates the maximum iterations, so the individual curves, computed only over runs that converge within this limit, do not exceed it.

Figure 1(a) numerically investigates the convergence rate of the TRM-SOP for the problems GGTZ8–DGO2, GGCZ18–BQT2, GGTZ2–ZDT4, and GGTZ13–Trigonometric taken from Ghosh et al. (2025b). The tolerance is set to $\epsilon = 10^{-4}$ (instead of $\epsilon = 10^{-3}$) to provide a better depiction of the algorithm’s convergence pattern. For each problem, we run the algorithm for 100 randomly selected initial points. The horizontal axis represents the iteration k , while the vertical axis represents the mean error value at that iteration. The mean is computed over the runs/initial points that reach iteration k (out of the total 100 runs).

From the figure, we observed that the error curves (cyan, blue, pink, red colored curves for GGTZ13-Trigonometric, GGTZ8-DGO2, GGTZ2-ZDT4, GGTZ16-BQT2 respectively) exhibit an approximately straight-line decreasing trend as the iterations increase. Such a behavior in a log-scale error plot indicates that the error decreases by roughly a constant multiplicative factor at each iteration. This geometric reduction of the error is characteristic of linear convergence, where the error satisfies a relation of the form $e_{k+1} \approx \frac{\xi}{1-\xi} e_k$, for some constant $0 < \xi < \frac{1}{3}$ (as established in Theorem 2), which is of the general form $e_{k+1} \approx c e_k$ for some constant $0 < c < 1$. Therefore, the observed behavior of the error curves provides numerical evidence supporting the theoretical linear convergence result of the TRM-SOP method.

Figure 1(b) examines the iteration complexity of the TRM-SOP algorithm and numerically verifies the theoretically derived iteration bound of $O(\epsilon^{-2})$. The figure shows iteration curves (green, red, pink, cyan) for four problems—GGTZ13-Trigonometric, GGTZ9-Hill, GGTZ2-ZDT4, and GGCZ15-BQT1—taken from Ghosh et al. (2025b). The horizontal axis represents the tolerance level ϵ , and the vertical axis shows the number of iterations k required for the error to reach that tolerance. The tolerance values are varied as $[0.005, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3]$.

From the figure, we observe that as ϵ decreases, the number of iterations gradually increases for all four problems, consistent with the theoretical dependence on ϵ . All curves remain below the blue analytical iteration bound, supporting the theoretical result. The black line represents the maximum iteration limit of 100 used in the experiments. Since the plotted values are computed only over runs that converge within this limit, the curves for individual problems do not cross the black line.